

**ENGLISH LANGUAGE: A VERITABLE TOOL FOR NATIONAL DEVELOPMENT IN
NIGERIA**

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Abstract

English language is the engine that drives all forms of development in Nigeria. First, it is a unifying factor in our multilingual nation. It is also the language of political administration, and most importantly, it is the language of education in Nigeria. Education is unarguably an essential instrument for change and for human and national development. The quality of education in a country underpins the growth of individual and national wealth and helps to drive economic development. This paper submits that if English language is the medium through which the concepts in education are expressed and acquired in this country; then, it is a veritable tool for both human and national development in Nigeria. Apart from this, English language has conferred a lot of privileges on Nigeria, both on the home front and the global scene. It has advanced Nigeria socially, politically, economically and technologically. This paper therefore suggests that new methods be injected into the issue of English language education, considering its importance to national development. The paper draws its inspiration from the theory of Community Language Learning (CLL) to achieve this lofty ideal.

Keywords: English language, Education, National development, Community language learning